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A novel approach for GSM estimation of woven fabric using yarn and fabric image analysis

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Abstract

Fabric weight measurement is crucial in textile industries as it provides a quantitative measure of fabric quality and influences fabric comfortability and serviceability during use. Fabric weight is expressed as the weight per unit area where gram per square meter (GSM) is the most popular unit. Current methods for measuring GSM in woven fabric have several limitations and challenges, like time-consuming procedures, possible damage to the fabric, and changes in measurement accuracy. This study presents a new method for measuring GSM in woven fabric that overcomes the limitations of current methods. The proposed method offered non-destructiveness, ensuring minimal impact on fabric integrity. In this process, advanced image analysis techniques for both yarn and fabric images are applied where warp and weft density along with yarn diameter are obtained from the image analysis. This information is used in GSM calculation by the developed program itself to provide the result. After developing the image analysis-based algorithm, the accuracy of the proposed method has sincerely evaluated in comparison with the results obtained by conventional methods measured with GSM cutters. It demonstrates the effectiveness of the developed method in providing reliable GSM measurements.

Keywords: Image analysis, GSM, yarn density, yarn diameter

1. Introduction

The geometrical characteristics of the fabric have several measures and weight of the fabric is one of them. Grams per square meter (GSM) is popular for expressing the fabric weight [1]. A woven fabric is a two-dimensional lattice structure where the lattice is constituted of

longitudinal warp yarn and horizontal weft yarn in cross combination. Observing the periodic arrangement of the surface contours is an effective method to study the fabric structure. The surface contours are associated with the yarn faces and enclosed by neighboring two yarns [2]. An electronic balance is used in the traditional GSM measurement method, where mostly destructive ways of fabric cutting are used, resulting in a significant amount of fabric waste. Approximately 3-5% of the total fabric is taken out from the process due to the testing procedure [3]. To address this issue, non-destructive methods are essential for controlling fabric utilization and manufacturing costs. Currently, methods involve the use of a GSM round cutter, which extracts precision-cut samples without damaging the fabric. After weighing the samples by using an electronic weight scale, the average weight is used to get the GSM value. In an alternative technique, magnifier lenses and inspector can be used, having a non-destructive nature but causing a labor-intensive workflow due to manual measurement systems.

The basic structural parameters of fabric can be analysed on an intensive scale with digital image analysis [4]. Basic structural parameters like yarn diameter, yarn count, etc., are convenient to measure through image processing [2]. It is a non-destructive method for determining fabric GSM involves utilizing a predictive formula given below [5],

$$GSM = \left(\frac{EPI}{\text{Warp Count}} + \frac{PPI}{\text{Weft Count}} \right) \times (100 + \text{Crimp}\%) \times 0.2327 \quad (1)$$

EPI and PPI imply the thread density of longitudinal warp and transverse weft yarn in the woven structure. This method relies on knowing the weft and warp counts of the fabric. A human with a magnifier, ruler and some other tools measures the GSM in a conventional manner

by counting the thread density and identifying the weave pattern. But this visual observation technique requires a huge amount of time and wears out the laboratory worker quickly due to its tedious work nature. Radiometric absorption enables X-ray sensors to absorb X-ray beams, which depends on the weight and density of the woven fabric. The absorption depends on the fabric weight. But this process has a 0.4 g/m² accuracy level [6]. Capacitive sensors can be used to measure the yarn mass when the yarn is placed between two capacitor plates [7]. The capacitance value changes with the change in mass between the plates. However, it creates trouble when measuring fabric mass in the weaving process as it shows a large fluctuation in the capacitance value [6]. To separate the fabric image into two sub-images, a laplacian mask is used where it needs to be applied in both the horizontal and vertical direction of the fabric. One sub-image only contains the warp yarns, while the other contains the wefts [8], [9]. The separated images are used to outline the yarn boundaries by further analysis. This helps to characterize the fabric surface in a deep manner [10]. CCD cameras with zoom lenses can be used to capture the fabric images, which are then converted into grayscale images with 256 grey levels. Two sub-images are produced from the original image by applying a Laplacian mask. EPI and PPI are calculated from the images, which are then used to measure the GSM value [5]. Thread density can be measured by Fourier transform analysis, where fabric images are processed via 2D fast Fourier transformation, resulting in an amplitude spectrum. Threshold segmentation, Fourier filtering and image reconstruction are done to obtain the thread density [11]. As a part of the continuous development initiatives for non-destructive GSM measurements, designing and developing an image processing system was the main objective of this study. A program was written to measure the fabric weight (GSM) in an automated manner. The proposed solution aims to overcome these challenges by designing and developing equipment for non-destructive fabric GSM measurement.

2. Methodology

2.1 Materials

Woven fabric made of cotton was used to establish the program and assess the code's and program's functionality. WL Professional Full HD Monitor Stereo Microscope was

used to capture the images of fabric and yarn.

2.2 Methods

Python language was used to write the code and develop an automated program where the image of the tested woven fabric and yarn was inserted. From the woven fabric image, the thread density of the fabric was measured and from the yarn photo, the diameter was measured via the code of the program.

Figure 1. Work flow of the GSM measurement

With the EPI, PPI and the count of the yarn, the GSM of the fabric can be calculated by the following equation [12]:

$$GSM = \left(\frac{EPI \times (1 + \text{crimp}\%)}{\text{Warp Count}} + \frac{PPI \times (1 + \text{crimp}\%)}{\text{Weft Count}} \right) \times 23.25 \quad (2)$$

The program provided processed images, thread density, and yarn pixels as the result of the computer monitor while the program was run.

3. Result and Discussion

In the developed program, the images of the fabric and yarn were inserted (Figure 2). Fabric images would be processed to find the EPI and PPI of the fabric and from the yarn image, the diameter and count of the yarn would be published. As a fabric sample was taken where warp and weft yarns were of the same count, a single image was required to be inserted. In the case of different yarn counts, two images (one for the warp and the other for the

Figure 2. Sample images of the (a) woven fabric and (b) yarn

Figure 3. Step of processing the inserted fabric image

Figure 4. Processing steps of the inserted yarn image

Figure 5. Displayed results in the developed program

weft yarn) were required to input.

Crimp of the warp yarn and crimp of the weft yarn were also given in the fixed blank cell of the program. This value will be used as per equation (2) alongside other information derived from the processed images.

The developed program successfully processed the woven structure image to count the number of warp and weft yarn per inch (Figure 3).

The image of the yarn was processed in a similar way to get the pixel of the main yarn body thickness (Figure 4).

The result from both the images was displayed on the monitor (Figure 5).

By taking multiple observations with the known yarn thickness, it was found that each inch's yarn diameter is equal to 15080 pixels of the image. As we got 98 pixels from the given yarn image, the yarn is 0.0065 inches in diameter by the conversion calculation. In the given sample, both the warp and weft yarn were in the same dimension and count.

The diameter of the yarn is related to the count through the following equation [1]:

$$\text{Count (Ne)} = \left(\frac{1}{28 \times \text{yarn diameter (inches)}} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

The count of the warp and weft is $\left(\frac{1}{28 \times 0.0065} \right)^2$ or 30.2 Ne.

After getting the yarn count and thread density from the developed program, the GSM was measured using equation (2). The warp crimp was 3% and the weft crimp was 5% in the sample.

$$\text{GSM} = \left(\frac{130 \times (1 + 3\%)}{30.2} + \frac{120 \times (1 + 5\%)}{30.2} \right) \times 23.25$$

$$\text{GSM} = 200.1$$

By image analysis, without any damage or destruction of the sample fabric, the result was produced in an automatic and faster process.

A total of three readings were taken by the developed program from the same fabric and this same fabric was cut by an 11.29 cm diameter GSM cutter manually, followed by the weight measurement of three cut samples of 100 cm² area. The comparative results from this manual

measurement and developed program are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Obtained GSM from the manual test and developed program

No. of Observations	Readings from the GSM cutter	Average (by GSM cutter)	Readings from the developed program	Average (by developed program)
1	190		200.1	
2	192	190.67	215.4	207.3
3	190		206.3	

The results showed an error of 10-20 range. This error can be reduced by conducting more trials for the required optimization of the developed program.

4. Conclusions

The developed program requires no weight measurement or sample cutting. Only captured images of the fabric and yarn are needed. However, the images should be taken in good lighting and with good camera quality. As an initiative to find a non-destructive method to measure the fabric GSM, it was successful as both the thread density and yarn diameter were measured properly. Only the input of the fabric and yarn images with the crimp of the warp and weft yarns were required. But more work can be done in the future. The quality of images still needs to be at a proper level; otherwise, the counting and measurement may fluctuate. The impact of yarn TPI and the specific density of the fibre were not considered during this development work. The impact of these two parameters can be assessed in future works.

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Conflict of Interest

No conflict of interest is reported.

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